

ICT Education and Employment Disparities: A Comparative Study of Developed and Developing Countries

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Abstract: The present paper investigates the gap in ICT-integrated market levels between developed and developing economies of the world expounding internet broadband penetration, GDP, and R&D efforts. Developed countries generally have high systems, extensive internet coverage and a lot of resources directed towards research activities while developing countries tend to have low levels of digital literacy, research funding and even the training of the ICT practitioners. The paper uses the ICT employment data for 10 countries from the year 2007 to 2020. The authors reveal that, contrary to R&D-investments, which promote ICT employment significantly, GDP by itself is not a sufficient driver of such developments across various countries. In developed nations, the robust telecommunication networks encourage high growth and higher levels of employability in the ICT sector. In contrast, developing countries encounter horizontal barriers that inhibit advances in ICT employment. The suggested measures are as follows: developed countries are encouraged to continue investing in ICT infrastructure and innovation, while developing countries should improve the physical access, increase R&D spending and build a stronger education system with ICT elements. These concerns have been raised in view of the need to positively influence growth in equity in ICT employment, as envisioned in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations. These measures are designed to provide access to good education and stimulation of economic activities alongside social integration to attain a digital economy that accommodates everyone across the globe.

Keywords: ICT Employment Disparities, Digital Divide, ICT Education, Internet Access, R&D Investment

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Accepted: 28 November, 2024; **Published:** 29 November, 2024

How to cite this article: Md Shahriar Kabir Sajib, Golam Mahadi, Ireash Roy, Md Muzahidul Islam (2024). ICT Education and Employment Disparities: A Comparative Study of Developed and Developing Countries. *North American Academic Research*, 7(11), 11-19. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14246913>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

The effect of ICT on education systems and the use of a workforce in other countries has really shaped economic aspects for the last couple of decades. It has transformed old industries, created new ones, and allowed connectivity amongst people across geographical boundaries (Lee et al., 2018). However, its contribution goes beyond restructuring industries; it has also become an important means of social mobility, where access to knowledge, jobs, and routes to economic progress have been provided to the citizens (Alfaraz & Tully, 2024). This is particularly true for innovation, which is driven by the automation, efficiency, and creation of new industries that ICT allows and promotes. Examples

of such technology-driven industries include software development, artificial intelligence, and data analytics (Wu, 2022). Among countries, economies with good ICT ecosystems are usually more productive and internationally competitive, a scenario occurring when the adoption of ICT decreases organizational costs and allows access to international markets more easily. For individuals in the current era, ICT skills are no longer a luxury but a necessity in order to be able to work (Stofkova et al., 2022). In this day and age where everything is almost computerized employment possibilities are dependent on ICT skills from basic computer skills to advanced programming skills.

Thus, education systems are premised on the fact that students should be provided with ICT skills (Timotheou et al., 2023). The countries which have better educational policies and curriculum that incorporates ICT in education assist learners to cultivate skills such as digital literacy and problem-solving at an early age (Hübner et al., 2023). In terms of developing student skills for the purpose of working in a knowledge economy, these skills are also necessary for ensuring the students' interaction with such opportunities. Countries such as Canada, Germany, and Sweden have made a lot of efforts by providing schools with modern ICT devices and connectivity to the internet (Escueta et al., 2020). This includes most of the government policies aimed at making digital tools, improving e-learning platforms, and conducting training programs for teachers regarding the teaching of ICT. The economic policies are also solid in these countries, enabling them to spend hugely on R&D. In return, developed countries allow innovation to bloom and provide many well-paid jobs in ICT. Hence, employment rates consistently turn out to be high in these countries for the ICT sector.

Developing countries, like Argentina, Armenia, and India, have much catching up to do regarding the development of ICT capabilities (Avgerou et al., 2016). School facilities in these countries often lack the basic ICT infrastructure such as Internet access and digital devices. There is also a shortage of qualified teachers who can confidently impart effective ICT training. For instance, whereas developed countries may invest huge proportions of their GDP in education and integration of ICT, developing nations have very limited budgets; this compels governments to invest in shorter-term needs at the expense of long-term investments in technology (Rodriguez-Segura, 2022). Economic constraints also affect the ability of developing nations to invest in R&D, which is an important stimulant for innovation and employment opportunities in ICT (Choi & Cho, 2023a). Unable to commit adequate funding to R&D, these nations cannot develop indigenous technologies or nurture growth in local ICT industries. In this manner, it neither stimulates ICT sector job creation nor it compels most developing countries to consume external technology, hence aggravating the digital divide.

This led to what is generally called the 'digital divide': "In countries of different developments, within one country in most cases, there is inequality in the level of development of ICTs" (McNeely, 2024). Probably the first problem is the access to the technology where for instance most of the developed countries can boast of their classrooms with ICT gadgets and Wi-Fi connectivity such that students participate effectively in e-learning (Gerick et al., 2017). Contrarily most of the schools in the rural areas of developing nations do not have any form of access to the Web or even basic computer facilities which puts their pupils at a serious disadvantage (Wei, 2022). Economic resources are also an issue, with higher per capita GDP in developed countries allowing for continued investment in ICT infrastructure, education, and R&D. However, the narrow budgets of developing countries prohibit similar investments, and most communities are therefore left unserved and unable to develop the basic skills needed for ICT growth (Nedungadi et al., 2018). This eventually impacts the employability rate since the proportion of ICT education and training in developing countries is low, thus impacting lower employment rates in ICT-related fields. Because of this, too many people cannot compete in high-paying, technology-driven jobs, which contributes to economic inequality and restricts global economic participation.

The digital divide is a whole lot more than a national problem; rather, it is one with serious international implications (Qadikolaie et al., 2022). As long as developed countries keep building their ICT capabilities, they will maintain their dominance in the technology-based industries and consequently benefit economically from innovation (ICT-

Driven Economic and Financial Development, 2019). The developing countries, on their part, will further lag behind both economically and socially. This increasing inequality affects not only the individuals in developing nations but also restricts the potential of those countries to contribute to the global economy. The bridging of this gap would assist in making the global workforce more equitable and inclusive. Initiatives that prioritize ICT integration in education, increase R&D investments, and provide affordable technology solutions can help developing countries catch up (Kalolo, 2019). These efforts are critical for ensuring that the benefits of ICT are accessible to all, regardless of geographic or economic constraints.

Problem Statement

In as much as there is a worldwide call for digital transformation, there is a striking gap in the rate of ICT employment between developed and underdeveloped nations. This is influenced by several factors, including the disparity in access to technology, the economic status, and the level of ICT oriented education. While advanced nations have managed to develop networks which utilize ICT for side – economic and employment purposes, such nations as Kenya are still striving to close the gap. In addition, the ICT related gaps in the developing countries do not only narrow down the career opportunities of the individuals but also affect the economic growth of the country as a whole. The situation described above leads to the very important issues, what is the contribution of education regarding the utilization of ICT, for instance, Turner's and economic aspects on getting employed and how to eradicate such practices. It is important to carry out a structured study of these elements in order to understand why this is the case and what concrete ways there are to solve the problem.

Objectives

The present research seeks to address the gap in ICT employment between the global north and South through three main aims. The core aims of the present study include

1. To examine the nature of the associations of factors related to ICT education with the rates of ICT employment.
2. To determine the evidence of the causes of the disparities on ICT employment.
3. To proffer evidence-based recommendations to different sectors of the government and other stakeholders.

Research Questions

In order to achieve the objectives, the following research questions will be explored in the research.

1. What is the difference in ICT employment rates between developed and developing countries?
2. What is the effect of school internet access, GDP, and R&D expenditure on ICT employment rates?
3. Are the gaps in ICT employment that existed in 2007 and 2020 closing or increasing?

Significance of the Study

ICT employment brings not only individual opportunities but also drives the national economy and competitiveness through being one of the main parts in this regard. This study is important for a number of reasons (Jayaprakash & Pillai, 2022). The lack of infrastructures, inadequate funding for education, and limited R&D investments are affecting most developing nations to develop their human resources in ICT seriously (Bussell, 2006). This study will help the policymakers identify the most significant barriers to ICT employment to allow them to focus on the critical areas that need attention. For example, it can allow governments to target infrastructure projects that extend connectivity to underserved areas if the analysis identifies low internet access in schools as one of the main drivers of employment disparities. Where there is evidence that limited R&D funding is hampering innovation, for instance, policymakers may use that to create incentives for private sector investment or to commit more resources to public research institutions (Fudickar & Hottenrott, 2019). By filling these gaps, developing nations will not only equip the manpower with the required skills they would need to perform the ICT-related jobs but would also make themselves more economically resilient and competitive in the global market.

Investments in innovation, the workforce, and education must be a priority for developed countries wishing to maintain their leadership position in the global ICT sector (Shkarlet et al., 2019). Drawing on the results of this study, it is possible to evaluate other economic variables, such as GDP and R&D expenditure, which contribute to trends in ICT employment. This would, in turn, assist the developed nations in appropriately adjusting their policies toward continuous competitiveness at times when there is a rapid change in technology and the working population globally. This could also promote a deeper understanding of the comparative advantages and challenges that face different developed countries, showcasing best practices from which success has been obtained that might be replicable in other contexts. In this regard, developed nations will be able to keep abreast with new developments in ICT to ensure that their positions as leaders within the digital economy are consolidated.

The persistent disparity between developed and developing nations in ICT employment reflects a broader digital divide that limits opportunities for millions of people worldwide (Longoria et al., 2022). Considerable attention has been paid to these problems in this study so as to facilitate the construction of possible mechanisms to overcome such disparities in practice. Therefore, the study should orient the relevant agencies at the international and national levels, as well as the private sector, towards developing strategies that will ensure that ICT resources are fairly distributed, by emphasizing the importance of the internet, education, and financial resources. This divide must be bridged for it is not only kind but also necessary for the realization of a global economy that is actually inclusive. The digital revolution however empowers developing countries as it does the rest of the world in making it: innovation, trade and stability improved for everyone (Andreoni et al., 2021).

The result of this present study coincides with the Sustainable Development Goals set by the United Nations, notably SDG 4 (Quality Education), which involves inclusive and equitable quality education, assurance of digital literacy and ICT skills, and SDG 8, Decent Work and Economic Growth, which deals with the promotion of sustained economic growth and productive employment opportunities. Through this, the study also serves the purpose of these world projects as it advocates for the education and employment in the ICT sector. For example, integrating ICT facilities in schools in developing nations has the advantage of making the children ready to actively participate in the digital economy activities that will be geared towards achieving sustainable development (O'Sullivan et al., 2021). Otherwise, enhancing the presence of jobs in the ICT sector earns economic benefits, helps alleviate poverty as well as promote equity in society which aligns with the main aim of the SDGs (Abbas & Zaman, 2024).

Literature Review

The importance of Information and Communication Technology education in improving employability has been recognized both within the academic literature and by policymakers. Actually, ICT education gives the individuals the necessary digital competencies that are greatly sought by most sectors of the economy (Bejaković & Mrnjavac, 2020). The upsurge in technology usage among businesses has increased demand for ICT workers and, therefore, ICT competency has emerged as one of the major factors in determining employability within the contemporary labor market. In developed countries, the integration of ICT into educational curricula has been systematic and comprehensive (Saif et al., 2022). An early use of technology in education enables pupils to become comfortable and proficient in the use of ICT, thus creating a workforce that is ready and able to harness ICT to foster innovation and productivity. This has been attributed to higher rates of employment in the ICT economy, as these people are able to fit in the needs of the market. On the other hand, many developing countries face serious challenges in ICT education. Lack of access to technology, lack of funds, and a scarcity of trained educators impede the effective and efficient integration of ICT in the education system (Kalolo, 2019). This gap leads to a workforce that is not well-equipped for possible ICT-enabled jobs and therefore lowers employment rates in the sector. The lack of ICT education exacerbates existing economic disparities because those without digital skills will severely be challenged to compete effectively in the global job market (Sun et al., 2023).

The digital divide between developed and developing nations is chiefly marked by striking contrasts in the level of ICT infrastructure and economic endowment. The technological infrastructure of developed countries, with widespread high-speed internet access and modern telecommunications networks, along with ready availability of digital devices, supports not only ICT education but also the growth of ICT industries and employment opportunities (Xia et al., 2024). For developing countries, there are often insufficient ICT infrastructures, incomplete internet penetration, especially in rural areas, and a lack of access to technology at reasonable cost impede the integration of ICT into education and the economy (Shirazi & Hajli, 2021). Economic constraints further limit the ability of these countries to invest in upgrading infrastructure or expanding access. That has partly contributed to the vicious cycle where developing countries tend to fall further behind other nations in ICT adoption and innovation. Job opportunities are also affected by this disparity. This means that in economies without infrastructure in ICT, the establishment of firms for advanced technologies is less likely to occur, hence reducing demand for ICT workers (Ruffini et al., 2019). Furthermore, because the sectors of ICT are poorly developed, there are fewer opportunities for entrepreneurship and innovation, further limiting employment opportunities.

GDP per capita, internet access and R&D expenditure are some of the pivotal economic indicators in the development of the ICT sector and related job opportunities (Roztock et al., 2019). Higher GDP per capita in developed countries provides the requisite finance necessary to invest heavily in ICT infrastructure and education (Mubarak et al., 2020). Richer economies can provide more money for schools to purchase technology, train teachers, and develop curricula on ICT. This will provide an enabling environment to develop ICT skills in the population for a competent and competitive workforce. Internet connectivity is vital both for ICT education and industry development. All students can access online materials and e-learning and develop their digital literacy from a very young age in countries where there is nationwide internet access. For the workforce, it means opportunity for participation in the digital economy, allows flexibility for remote work, and enables innovation (Buchan et al., 2024). Conversely in poor countries, such opportunities are limited, especially to the people who have very little access to the internet, and such situations impede the development of education or even the ICT economy. Investment in R&D is very important aspect of adapting to and, more importantly, improving technology (Qadikolaei et al., 2022). In most economies that spend considerable amounts of money on R&D, such expenditures help in the development of new technologies, systems, and goods that may facilitate the opening of a new market and employment opportunities within the ICT industry (Choi & Cho, 2023b). Most developed countries have a higher R&D expenditure and are thus more apt to support a self-reinforcing cycle of innovation and growth. Developing countries, which spend less on R&D, will be behind the pace of technological change and hence less competitive in enabling ICT-related jobs.

Research Gaps

Even though there exist extensive published works on various effects of ICT education, infrastructure disparity and economic factors separately on employment, literature still has several notable gaps. One such gap is the absence of comprehensive assessment such as the rate of schools having internet access, GDP per capita and spending on research and development in ICT to the ICT employment rates. These studies have, by and large, focused on these factors in isolation, which fails to capture the complex interactions and interdependencies between these factors. More comparative studies that investigate these factors in how they influence ICT employment in developed versus developing countries are not many. This will be vital in bringing out the special challenges and opportunities faced by each group, and strategies in which disparities can be addressed. Another significant gap is the lack of longitudinal studies that examine trends over an extended period of time, such as from 2007 to 2020. Longitudinal analyses will be essential in identifying trends, assessing impacts due to policy changes, and comprehending the impact of global events on the disparities in ICT employment. There is, finally, a need for more country-specific studies since these are also able to

control for particular cultural, political, and economic contexts that matter for ICT education and employment. Thus, addressing the aforementioned gaps will be important in order to provide a fuller and more nuanced view of the forces pushing the ICT employment gap and for targeted policy interventions.

Addressing these gaps, this study offers a comprehensive quantitative analysis by integrating multiple variables like Internet access in schools, GDP per capita, and R&D expenditure into one analytical framework. These will provide a more holistic understanding of the factors influencing ICT employment rates by capturing their interactions and combined effects. Besides this, the study gives much in the way of insight through comparison by directly considering the relative dynamics and challenges faced within selected developed countries-namely, Canada, Germany, Sweden, the USA, and the UK-and developing countries such as Argentina, Armenia, China, India, and Chile. This comparison sheds light on what factors are more or less responsible for the ICT employment in such economic environments. The longitudinal approach is also used as the study spans from 2007 to 2020. This enables the study to be able to find how the disparities in ICT employment have been shaped by different trends over that time. Additionally, the study provides policy-relevant results through underlining the main areas where intervention is critical, hence proposing evidence-based recommendations that support equitable growth in the area of ICT employment. These are insights which shall help policymakers in devising potentially actionable strategies that could reduce the digital divide and further inclusive economic development.

Methodology

Study Design

This study focuses on the quantitative research approach to analyzing disparities in ICT employment between developed and developing countries. In this regard, the analysis uses secondary data sourced from reliable sources such as World Development Indicators, Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, and Statista. This section examines the possible differences between developed and developing nations in ICT employment and its correlates. The research framework incorporates elements that help to explain the determinants of ICT employment and provides practical recommendations.

The sample is purposive and consists of ten countries, two groups of five representing developed and developing countries. Developed countries are Canada, Germany, Sweden, the United States, and the United Kingdom, while developing countries are Argentina, Armenia, China, India, and Chile. These countries were chosen to make sure that there are sufficiently many economic as well as geographic contexts that will allow for an effective comparison of the differences that prevail in ICT engagement. The criteria used to select these countries were multifold. The developed countries-for example, Canada, Germany, Sweden, the United States, and the United Kingdom-offer well-established infra system elements related to ICT education and employment. Their advanced economies and heavy investments in R&D serve as a yardstick against which one understands the conditions that promote growth in ICT employment. On the other hand, developing countries such as Argentina, Armenia, China, India, and Chile have been selected on account of the different stages of ICT development and their unique regional challenges. It includes countries, both those that are really potential emerging economies to grow along with ICT and those plagued by infrastructural and economic impediments to growth. The study comprises a wide range of economies, social structures, distribution of power, levels of development, geographical spread, and capacities in ICT by bringing both developed and developing countries on board, in order to fully understand and appreciate the variations in ICT employment and offer relevant solutions that fit different scenarios.

Research Hypotheses

The study is guided by the following research questions and their corresponding hypotheses.

RQ 1 What are the differences in ICT employment rates between developed and developing countries?

H0 There is no significant difference in ICT employment rates between developed and developing countries.

H1 Developed countries have significantly higher ICT employment rates compared to developing countries.

RQ 2 How do internet access in schools, GDP, and R&D expenditure influence ICT employment rates?

H0 There is no significant relationship between internet access in schools and ICT employment rates.

H1 Higher internet access in schools positively impacts ICT employment rates.

H0 GDP does not significantly influence ICT employment rates.

H1 GDP positively impacts ICT employment rates.

H0 R&D expenditure does not significantly influence ICT employment rates.

H1 Increased R&D expenditure positively impacts ICT employment rates.

RQ 3 Are ICT employment disparities narrowing or widening from 2007 to 2020?

H0 There has been no significant change in ICT employment disparities between 2007 and 2020.

H1 ICT employment disparities between developed and developing countries have significantly changed over the period.

Econometric Model

$$EMP_ICT_{it} = \beta_0 + \sum_{k=1}^3 \beta_k X_{kit} + \beta_4 \cdot GRP_i + \sum_{k=1}^3 \gamma_k \cdot GRP_i \cdot X_{kit} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Where,

EMP_ICT_{it} is dependent variable ICT Employment rate for country i at time t.

X_{kit} is independent variables indexed by k

$k1$ = Internet access in school

$k2$ = Per capita GDP

$k3$ = R&D Expenditure

$\beta_0, \beta_k, \gamma_k$ and β_4 are the intercept term and coefficients

ϵ_{it} shows the error term.

The focus of the econometric model is to investigate the factors that determine the employment of ICT in numerous countries over time, but with emphasis on the variations on developed and less developed economies. The dependent variable refers to the ICT employment rate for a country in question at a specific period. The model includes the most essential independent variables which convey primary assumptions about how most ICT employment is created and these include school internet access per capita, GDP, and research and development expenditure. These aspects entail ICT systems, the economy, and enhancements as regards effects on employment. Moreover, the model has an additional explanatory variable of group membership developed- developing countries which assist in explaining how

these structural determinants of ICT employment operate in each group. In this course, interaction terms are used to investigate if the independent variables have the same impact on these two groups providing a perfect explanation of the presence of distinct opportunities and challenges in both groups. In the model, unobserved factors and random shocks are also integrated owing to the presence of an error term which guarantees that only systematic relationships between the variables are analyzed. The model gives a holistic explanation of the factors responsible for the disparities in ICT employment and also provides useful information to the various stakeholders who are interested in reducing these disparities on a global scale.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive statistics

The analysis of the key variables indicated significant differences especially as regards; GDP, access to the internet (INT_User), research and development expenditure (RDE) and the level of employment in ICT (EMP_ICT). The GDP figures are highly skewed between countries, as they range from -13.5 to 14.5, which can be understood as the difference between developed countries and developing ones. The median GDP is 1.8 while the mean is 1.885 indicating that the majority of the countries GDP'S are low, however, there are a few who have high GDP'S which are pulling the mean of the figure upwards. The internet access (INT_User) is also highly variable, ranging between 4% and 97%. Although, the median value of 75% implies that half of the countries have considerable internet access, the mean standing at 65.34% indicates that a few countries have very low levels of internet access thus causing a left skewed distribution. The R&D (RDE) expenditure falls between 0.18% and 3.49% of GDP which signifies great tolerance in the level of funds allocated to research and development. The Averaging 1.71% median correlated closely to the 1.666% mean, suggesting that these countries are somewhat similar in terms of their GDP devoted to R&D expenditure, although still with some notable distinctions on extremes of spenders. Rates of employment in ITC (EMP_ICT) display a range of 1.0 to 5.2, a clear illustration of the scope in which countries build their workforce in terms of the ICT sector. While the median of 2.8 and the mean of 2.854 indicate perhaps a normal distribution, most of the countries in the figure appear to be fitted within the range of 2.2 – 3.4 ICT employment rates. Generally, the data set exemplifies a high degree of variability in terms of the economic level, the infrastructure and the ICT index for various countries. It is expected that the high GDP levels, internet access, R&D budget and ICT employment rates will be mostly exhibited by developed countries, while the majority of the developing countries will be found in the lower quartiles. (Table 1).

Table 1

	GDP	INT_User	RDE	EMP_ICT
Min.	:-13.500	Min. : 4.00	Min. :0.180	Min. :1.000
1st Qu.:	0.400	1st Qu.:45.75	1st Qu.:0.560	1st Qu.:2.200
Median :	1.800	Median :75.00	Median :1.710	Median :2.800
Mean :	1.885	Mean :65.34	Mean :1.666	Mean :2.854
3rd Qu.:	4.850	3rd Qu.:87.00	3rd Qu.:2.732	3rd Qu.:3.400
Max. :	14.500	Max. :97.00	Max. :3.490	Max. :5.200

Source: Author

Regression Analysis

The results of the regression analyses shed some light on the interaction among the employment rates of ICT and the independent variable reasons of GDP, Internet Users and R&D expenditure. The coefficient of -0.0080 for GDP portrays a weak negative association with the ICT employment rate. Nevertheless, this relationship is not statistically meaningful since it has a p-value of 0.5320. Moreover, the R2R2R2 measure of 0.0058 and especially the negative ad-

justed R2 of -0.0089 at the last stage of analysis indicate that GDP contributes very little to the explanation of the variances in ICT employment rates and as such should not be included in the current analysis. Unlike the GDP variable, growth in the number of Internet Users is very strongly and positively correlated with the ICT employment rate, and the relationship is statistically significant. The coefficient of 0.0119 indicates that for the ICT employment, a 1% increase in the usage of the internet translates to an increase of 0.0119 units. The p-value is very small (0.0000), thus this relationship is regarded as significant. On the other hand, the R2 value of 0.2826 and the adjusted R2 of 0.2721 show that the level of usage of the internet accounts for about 28.26% of the fluctuations in the rates of employment in the ICT sector, thus a large effect on the employment in ICT, J82. In the same way, the provision of R&D investment is another predominant factor affecting the ICT employment rate with the coefficient standing at positive 0.2935. This indicates that 1 units increase in the R&D expenditure on GDP basis leads to a 0.2935 rise in the ICT employment rate. The p-value being 0.0049 shows that this relationship is statistically significant. The R2 value of 0.1105 and adjusted R2 of 0.0974 further show that the R&D expenditure accounts for 11.05% of the change in the ICT employment rates which is less than the contribution of the internet usage but still shows an appreciable effect as well (Table 2).

Table 2

Table: Summary of Regression Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-value	p-value	R-Squared	Adjusted R-Squared
GDP	-0.0080	0.0127	-0.627	0.5320	0.0058	-0.0089
Internet Users	0.0119	0.0023	5.176	0.0000	0.2826	0.2721
R&D Expenditure	0.2935	0.1010	2.906	0.0049	0.1105	0.0974

Source: Author

So, in summary, the findings of this study indicate that the use of the Internet and the spending on R&D are important factors determining the percentages of ICT employment, with the former being the strongest of all. In this case, the GDP turns out not to be an important explanatory factor for the rates of ICT employment. The implications of these findings point more towards making the Internet more available and putting more resources into R&D for ICT employment enhancement than relying simply on the economic growth, as represented by GDP alone (Figure 1).

The two scatter plots explore the destruction of a bi-variable factor which is the ICT employment rates in both developed and developing economies and some other factors (i.e. comprising internet usage, gdp growth and R&D expenditure). In farm one graph where all the development dollar countries is plotted, it is clear that even as the high levels of the other associated variable are obtained, the levels of ICT employment do not seem to improve considerably. The employment rate trend line and score also show that developed economies posted moderate combined variable scores that had a great impact on employment in ICT. The employment rates in this category have approximately 2 to 8 percent levels but there is a significant dispersion around the trend line as countries vary in the extent to which the combined variables have been or can be effectively employed (Figure 2).

In the second plot where the relationship applies to the case of developing nations similar trends can be seen but the employment growth trend in less developed countries is not very steep when compared to developed nations. This means that the combined variable is not as effective in driving up ICT employment rates in developing countries as it is in developed countries. The employment rate of developing countries is between 1% and 3%, much lower than that of the developed countries. In addition, the data points are concentrated around the trend line, implying a smaller range in the variables (Figure 3).

Source: Author

In the analysis of the two scatter plots, it can be observed that countries that are considered developed have more rate of ICT employment and greater effect of the composite index which is defined as a combination of internet use, GDP growth, and research and development expenditures over the employment growth. The rates of employment in the ICT sector in the developed regions vary between 2 percent to as high as 8 percent breaching ICT orientation depending on its GDP and technological advancement. The regression line shows a steep diagram that implies most factors in ICT employment growth in these countries cut across internet and research and development R&D facilities. This is anticipated because these countries have high levels of developed networks, fast internet is available in the major investments, high investments in research and development, and high education with integration of ICT training in the education system that equips the labor market. Such factors created a situation where economic growth, technology and creative ideas engendered a strong demand for ICT related job. On the other hand, employment rates in the sector of information and communications technology for developing countries are substantially less where they do not go beyond 1% - 3% with the trend line also being less steep. This means that the composite index does not have a strong influence on the growth of employment in the ICT sector in these countries. Such a difference is however also evident in those differences due to systems related issues such as general access to cheap, stable and fast internet, economic

growth rate also slow relative to the developed world and research and development budgets that are almost zero. Several nations classified as developing countries also fail to put in place basic facilities like internet in offices and schools so as to enhance the skills of ICT and its integration in these services. Furthermore, due to the lack of appropriate R&D funding, developing countries are unable to avail of advanced technology since it limits innovativeness, critical in creating.

Limitations

This research, despite shedding light on some important issues regarding the ICT employment rates, has its shortcomings. One of the shortcomings is that the study heavily relies on secondary data sources such as the global database and global reports which may contain inconsistencies and unavailability of data or even bias in the measure of the data. Furthermore, the geographical scope of the study is limited to a few developed and developing nations which restricts the extrapolation of the findings to the different regions with different socioeconomic or technological features. Another shortcoming is the limitation to only quantitative effects which ignores important considerations like the effect of political stability, societal disposition towards technology, or even the existing policies that affect employment creation in the ICT sector. This could help in identifying the barriers and the drivers of ICT employment that is particular to each country. In this regard, the study's emphasis on econometric and infrastructural variables which are measurable captures substantively may neglect such aspects.

Future Research

Such shortcomings as above should be rectified in the future research by broadening the analysis and going into it in greater depth. Expansion into additional territories, particularly into (emerging) less developed regions, will assist in gaining more comprehensive understanding of global tendencies regarding employment in the field of information and communication technologies. Adding more precise statistics, such as the employment rate of ICT in different sectors or rural vs urban estimates, would help improve the analysis as well. Additional interesting exploration in the same area could be research of such factors as digital literacy or types of government or business ICT practices, which might relate to ICT employment. It would be beneficial if such studies were to include research design which employs qualitative methods such as interviews and case studies, while also using much short quantitative methods within the larger qualitative write-up in order to provide research context that would include the culture, politics or organizations. Such approaches would mean that future studies would be more flexible and richer in interventions in relation to ICT employment inequities in any context.

Conclusion

This paper points to large differences in the ICT employment rates of developed and developing countries, identifying the key factors that drive such differences. It emerges from the findings that internet access and R&D expenditure are the critical drivers of ICT employment, as shown by the strong and statistically significant positive relationships of both variables with employment rates. The converse happens with the GDP alone, which fails to emerge as a significant predictor, indicating that broader economic performance becomes less important than targeted investments in technology and innovation. With their better infrastructure, higher R&D investments, and wider internet diffusion, there are many more workers employed in ICTs in developed countries. In developing nations, persistent concerns include minimal Internet connectivity and insufficient R&D funding. These results, therefore, point to the need for strategic interventions in these disparities and harnessing ICT as a catalyst for economic development. In light of these issues, sustaining leadership in developed countries requires that their policy makers nurture their leadership through continuous

investment in internet infrastructure, R&D, and ICT skill-building through education and make sure internet accessibility is widespread to ensure innovative job creation. The priorities for developing countries should be to increase access to the internet, particularly in underserved regions, and to increase R&D investments for stimulating innovation and creating local ICT industries. Policies should be directed to forging partnerships with the private sector for financing technology adoption and skill-building programs, besides skills training programs that address the digital skills deficit and expand workforce participation in the ICT sector. It is important to consider ICT education and employment equity for global economic development in the face of an increasingly digitalized world. Overcoming structural barriers to ICT employment in developing countries and increasing sustained growth in developed economies will reduce the digital divide and foster inclusive economic participation. Investments in ICT infrastructure, innovation, and education are a means not only toward economic prosperity but also for empowerment in a global community and among individuals. With the global economy increasingly dependent on technology, ensuring equitable access to the opportunities created in ICT careers will be fundamental to sustainable development and long-term economic resilience. The study undertakes to highlight a number of coordinated efforts that must be made to create an inclusive and equitable digital future.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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